

FACTORS INFLUENCING UZBEK RETURNEES' READJUSTMENT AND REMIGRATION INTENTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the readjustment challenges and remigration intentions of Uzbek returnees from South Korea. Based on Kim's Re-Acculturation theory, the purpose is to understand the psychological and sociocultural processes involved in their readjustment. A mixed methods approach combining qualitative interviews and quantitative analysis of key factors influencing readjustment and remigration intentions was used. Results show that factors such as cultural differences, economic disparities, language barriers, and limited employment opportunities significantly influence the readjustment experience and contribute to remigration intentions. Based on the findings, it is suggested that targeted support programs addressing language skills, job training, and psychosocial support be developed to facilitate successful readjustment. These findings contribute to the understanding of return migration dynamics and inform policymakers and organizations on the interventions needed to improve the readjustment process of Uzbek returnees.

Keywords: re-adaptation, remigration, Uzbek returnees, Kim's re-adaptation theory, support programs.

1. Introduction

The reintegration of returnees into their home country after a period of migration presents unique challenges that require careful consideration and support. Scholars in global diaspora studies, migration studies, and related disciplines have extensively studied the complexities of return migration and its impact on individuals and societies (Brettell & Hollifield, 2022). This study focuses specifically on Uzbek returnees from South Korea to examine the issues they face upon return and explore the factors that contribute to their remigration. By drawing on a range of scholarly perspectives and empirical evidence, we can gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges Uzbek returnees face in reintegration and develop practical solutions and theoretical approaches to help policymakers make informed decisions. In the field of global diaspora studies, researchers have highlighted the multi-faceted nature of returnee experiences. The process of reintegration involves not only the physical return to the home country, but also the renegotiation of identities, the adjustment to social and cultural norms, and the re-establishment of networks and relationships. The literature offers valuable insights into the various factors that shape the reintegration process, such as economic conditions, social support networks, access to resources, and the interplay between the migrants' host and home countries (King, 2012). Migration research provides a broader context for understanding the challenges faced by returnees. Scholars have examined the push and pull factors that drive migration, the social and economic dynamics of host countries, and the structural obstacles that returning migrants encounter upon return. Comparative studies across regions and countries have shed light on the different experiences of returnees and highlighted the role of contextual factors in shaping their reintegration pathways.

In addition, theories and frameworks on re-acculturation and reverse culture shock have provided valuable insights into the psychological and sociocultural processes involved in returning to the home country. In

particular, Kim's re-acculturation theory (2001) provides a conceptual framework that allows us to further examine the challenges Uzbek returnees face when returning to their familiar but changed homeland. By applying this theory, we can analyze the interplay between individual experiences and broader societal factors, ultimately providing a more nuanced understanding of the reintegration process. Drawing on the wealth of knowledge accumulated in global diaspora studies, migration studies, and related fields, this study aims to contribute to the existing literature by focusing specifically on the experiences of Uzbek returnees from South Korea. By examining the challenges they face upon return and identifying the factors that influence their return decisions, we can offer practical recommendations and theoretical insights to policymakers. This research will provide a comprehensive understanding of the reintegration process and contribute to the development of effective support mechanisms that promote the successful and sustainable reintegration of Uzbek returnees in Uzbekistan.

2. Literature Review

The experiences of returning migrants have received considerable attention in migration studies (Adda et al., 2022), with a focus on understanding the challenges and dynamics associated with their reintegration and re-acculturation process (White, 2022). This literature review aims to provide an overview of the major theories, approaches, and studies related to returning migrants, with a particular focus on their experiences of readjustment and re-acculturation. By examining the existing literature, it will highlight the factors that influence the readjustment process, comparative studies, factors of returnees, and possible solutions to the challenges facing returning migrants (Porru & Baldo, 2022). In addition, studies that address the causes of return migration and provide insights into the complex dynamics that shape return migration will be examined. Various theories and approaches have been developed to understand the experiences of returning

migrants. One prominent theory is Kim's re-acculturation theory (2001), which focuses on the psychological and sociocultural processes of reintegration. Kim highlights the challenges associated with renegotiating cultural identities, relearning social norms, and orienting to the sociocultural context of the home country. This theory provides a framework for understanding the complexity of return migration and its impact on individuals' well-being and sense of belonging. Numerous studies have examined returnees' experiences of readjustment and re-acculturation. For example, Compton-Lilly et al. (2017) conducted a qualitative study of returning migrants from the United States to Mexico and examined their experiences of cultural readjustment and identity negotiation. The study highlighted the challenges that returned migrants face in re-establishing their cultural identity and sense of belonging in their home country.

Comparative studies have helped to understand the differences and similarities in the reintegration experiences of returned migrants from different regions. For example, Mitchell et al. (2019) conducted a comparative study of return migrants from the United Kingdom to India and Australia and examined the factors that influence their re-acculturation process. The study found that cultural familiarity, language skills, and social support networks play a critical role in facilitating successful reintegration. Studies have also examined the factors, problems, and potential solutions related to returnees' reintegration experiences. Ceccagno & Gao (2022) examined the challenges that returning migrants face in accessing employment opportunities that match their skills and qualifications. The study emphasized the importance of tailored job placement programs and vocational training to effectively address this issue. Another important aspect of return migration research is understanding the causes of return migration. A study by Torres (2018) examined the factors that lead to the return migration of migrants from Latin America to their home countries. The study identified economic instability, limited social support, and difficulty reintegrating into the labor market as important factors contributing to return migration.

The literature reviewed above provides a comprehensive understanding of the complexity of the reintegration and re-acculturation experiences of returning migrants. The theories, approaches, and studies highlighted in this literature review serve as valuable resources for this article and contribute to the discussion of the challenges Uzbek returnees from South Korea face in their readjustment. By examining previous research on returnees, policymakers and organizations can develop effective support mechanisms, interventions, and strategies that address the specific needs and challenges of these returnees (Dadabaev & Soipov, 2020). In addition, the literature reviewed here highlights the importance of factors such as life course differences, occupation, economic reasons, and family responsibilities in shaping returnees' adjustment experiences, which can inform the development of targeted solutions and support systems for Uzbek returnees (Weitz, 2018). This literature review provides an overview of the theories, approaches, and studies related to

returnees, focusing on their experiences of reintegration and re-acculturation. Understanding the complexities of return migration is critical to developing effective strategies, policies, and support mechanisms that facilitate successful reintegration. So, by building on existing knowledge, researchers, policymakers, and organizations can improve reintegration experiences and promote the successful integration of returning migrants from South Korea to Uzbekistan.

3. Readjustment of return migrants.

Returning to one's home country after a long period of migration can be a complex and difficult process. Uzbek migrants returning from South Korea face several factors that affect their readjustment. These factors can affect their economic and social conditions, as well as their personal perceptions and well-being. In this opinion piece, we will explore the challenges Uzbek migrants face and the importance of understanding their experiences during the process of readjustment. An important perspective to consider is the objective criteria of readjustment. These include factors such as finding suitable employment, securing adequate housing, building personal relationships, and participating in community organizations. The success or failure of reintegration often depends on the fulfillment of these criteria (Johnson, 1975). When studying the reintegration of Uzbek migrants returning from South Korea, it is important to assess whether they have been able to meet these objective conditions of reintegration. In addition, the migrants' subjective perception of their adjustment plays an important role. The degree of satisfaction or dissatisfaction expressed by returnees reflects their personal assessment of their readjustment process (Gama, 1977). It is crucial to understand their perspectives and how they assess the extent to which their needs are being met and their overall well-being in their home country. Plans to emigrate again can serve as an indicator of dissatisfaction or maladjustment (Andreason, 2005).

Rohrlich (1991) assumes that return migrants, like migrants returning from developing countries, may face fewer obstacles and psychological costs in readjusting because of their familiarity with the destination country and existing social networks. However, the reality may be different. While some migrants readjust quickly and face minimal problems upon return, many others are disillusioned and dissatisfied. Despite possible economic advantages over their compatriots, they are dissatisfied with life in their home country. This phenomenon, known as "reverse culture shock," is observed among returnees from different countries (Oberg, 1960). Such dissatisfaction can even lead to a desire to emigrate again. Many returnees are ill-prepared for the changes that have taken place during their absence. Communities and individuals have evolved, and their traditional cultures may no longer match the new perspectives acquired during their time abroad. Former relationships may have become estranged, and returning migrants may feel they have become detached from their once-familiar surroundings. In extreme cases, some migrants even feel that they have more in common with people from the host society than with their compatriots (Sussman 2002).

The "way things are done at home" can also be a source of dissatisfaction. The slower pace, lack of efficiency, and bureaucratic inefficiencies can frustrate returning migrants who are used to the fast-paced, organized systems in their host countries. Complaints about government bureaucracy and corruption are not uncommon, highlighting the stark contrast between their experiences abroad and at home (Cassarino, 2004). It is worth noting that migrants often learn over time to cope with the challenges they face during re-acclimatization. Studies have shown that the adjustment period usually lasts between 1 and 2 years. Over time, the proportion of dissatisfied returnees tends to decrease. However, it is important to recognize that a proportion of returnees may decide to emigrate again due to persistent dissatisfaction.

4. Methods & Results

This study utilizes a research methodology that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative methods involve conducting interviews with a sample of Uzbek returnees to obtain first-hand accounts of their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms. Quantitative methods, on the other hand, involve identifying and defining the key factors that influence the reintegration process, as discussed in the following sections. A preliminary analysis of the available data shows that Uzbekistan and the Philippines rank fifth in terms of the number of migrants in South Korea. With about 55,000 people from each country, they account for about 3% of the total migrant population. However, it is important to be aware that these numbers may underestimate the true numbers due to undocumented migrants and limitations in official statistics. The general trend of South Korea attracting significant numbers of migrants (2.04 million in 2016) further contributes to the influx of Uzbek labor migrants seeking opportunities in the country. As the number of Uzbek returnees continues to increase, addressing the challenges they face during the reintegration process will be of utmost importance. This paper presents the findings of the study, highlights the experiences and needs of Uzbek returnees, and suggests possible solutions or measures to facilitate their successful reintegration. We also offer suggestions for developing comprehensive support mechanisms for Uzbek returnees in Uzbekistan based on globally recognized ideas and concepts. In the following sections, we address the specific challenges Uzbek returnees face, analyze available data, and provide recommendations for policymakers and organizations to improve the reintegration experience and facilitate the successful transition of Uzbek returnees from South Korea to Uzbekistan.

Furthermore, this study aims to enhance the scientific understanding of the experiences and factors influencing the return and readjustment process of migrants, with a particular focus on their intention to remigrate. Qualitative research methods have been used extensively to explore the subjective meanings attributed to these experiences and the interconnectedness of social factors that influence the lives of returnees. Through the use of qualitative methods, this research has gained valuable access to migrants' life narratives and their per-

sonal interpretations of reality, enabling a comprehensive understanding of their experiences before, during, and after return in terms of readjustment and reintegration. Furthermore, the use of in-depth interviews as a qualitative approach has facilitated the analysis of the interrelationships between the different factors influencing the readjustment process while providing insights into returnees' self-assessment of their overall well-being. *Interviews based on questions that fully opinion-sharing experience during the re-adaptation process:*

How do they navigate and interpret their lives after returning to their home country?

How do these factors affect their overall adjustment and reintegration?

What are the key factors that have influenced the readjustment process of Uzbek returnees?

The inclusion of *quantitative methods* in the second phase of this research aims to complement the qualitative findings by facilitating data collection and analysis of additional factors that influence the process of return and readjustment in migrants' respective home countries. Through the use of a mixed methods approach, it is expected that a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the topic will be gained, drawing on the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. From the quantitative section of the research, we analyze how do individual aspects such as life satisfaction, career opportunities, economic considerations, and family demands influence the readjustment process of Uzbek migrants returning from South Korea?

In the survey and interview, I planned to formulate questions and variables depending on the following question:

- *How have economic conditions, social factors, changes within their communities, and bureaucratic inefficiencies affected their ability to successfully reintegrate?*

- *Why do some Uzbek migrants returning from South Korea find reintegration into their home country more difficult than emigrating again to South Korea or another country?*

- *What are the reasons and dynamics underlying this phenomenon?*

- *How do Uzbek returnees deal with the difficulties they encounter during the reintegration process? What strategies do they use to overcome the challenges?*

1) Participant Profiles.

The current study incorporates the described experiences of 9 participants on their return to Uzbekistan from South Korea. Saturation was achieved with 9 participants as no new themes relevant to repatriation and the process of returning home were introduced, but the experiences highlighted by participants matched recurring themes. The names of all participants were changed to ensure their anonymity.

Although all participants had traveled independently to different overseas destinations, they all agreed that they had found their time abroad to be an enriching, even life-changing experience. There are several common themes in the participants' interviews

and their experiences of re-acclimatizing after their time abroad. However, the extent to which they experienced certain aspects and perceptions of the return process differed according to their individual backgrounds and circumstances. It is therefore essential to understand the participants' backgrounds, as described in this

section, in order to understand and properly analyze their perceptions of the reintegration process (Le, 2014). An overview of the participants can be found in Table 1.

Table 1

Participant summary as created by the researcher based on questions.

Name	Age & Sex	Overseas Country	Time of Sojourn	Time since return	Education	Occupation and workplace in Korea.
1.Bahrom	36, Male	Russia South Korea	5 years	11 months	Bachelor's degree	E9 visa, food industry company
2.Jasur	32, Male	South Korea	8 years	8 months	Master's degree in CNU.	E7 Samsung company
3.Bobur	29, Male	Kazakhstan South Korea	6 years	2 years	Bachelor's degree	Student, illegal worker
4.Kumush	33, female	Russia South Korea	5 years	12 months	Bachelor's degree	E9 visa, Hannam industry, factory
5.Nilufar	36, female	Singapore South Korea	10 years	5 months	Master's degree	E3, researcher Chosun University
6.Sherali	39, Male	South Korea	8 years	14 months	High school	E9, Sheep industry, Illegal worker
7.Mansur	41, Male	Russia South Korea	9 years	7 months	High school	E9, construction
8.Jamshid	34, Male	South Korea	5 years	3 years	High school	Illegal worker
9.Nargiza	28, Female	South Korea	3 years	6 months	Bachelor's degree	Student Yonsei University

Each participant had a story to tell, and they often enjoyed reliving some of their experiences abroad and sharing about their return and the process of re-acclimatization. The background and uniqueness of each participant are presented using information from the information provided during the interview. All participants were friendly and polite, communicated well, and showed obvious interest in participating in the study and sharing their personal experiences of returning to Uzbekistan. Some candidly shared detailed stories, while others were more guarded.

2) Volunteer and forced return.

Migration research focuses on understanding the experiences of migrants at different stages of their migration journey. When studying the experiences of migrants returning to Uzbekistan from South Korea, it is important to consider the different circumstances that lead to their return, including both voluntary and forced returns, to understand the process of return and reintegration of migrants, it is important to consider different categories of return. These include voluntary return, forced return for personal reasons and due to gender-related constraints in the life course, forced return due to structural constraints, and forced return (Table 2). Each category has unique factors that influence the decision to return and shape migrants' experiences.

Voluntary return involves a conscious decision to return home, free from external pressures. It is often associated with preparations, such as obtaining citizenship in the host country, saving money, or achieving specific goals. This type of return reflects the migrant's desire to put down roots and contribute to his or her community of origin.

Forced return for personal reasons and due to gender constraints in the life course occurs when migrants face challenges related to their well-being or family situation. For example, a female migrant may decide to return to see her children again, whom she cannot join in the host country. Furthermore, forced return is an involuntary process encouraged by either the home or the host country. It includes situations where migrants are forced to leave the country due to immigration status violations or criminal acts. This often involves administrative or legal procedures and may include detention. Understanding these categories of return offers valuable insights into the complex dynamics and motivations underlying migrant return and reintegration processes. It clarifies the different circumstances that influence their decisions and experiences when returning to their home countries.

Table 2

Factors Influencing Re-Adaptation Experience of Uzbek Returnees.

Context	Factors
Voluntary Return	- Mix of emotions and challenges upon arrival - Difficulty readjusting to home country due to lifestyle changes, cultural differences, and economic disparities
Forced Return	- Greater challenges and negative emotions due to involuntary return - Disruption of established life and social networks
Reintegration Difficulties	- Difficulty finding employment opportunities that match skills and qualifications - Cultural adjustments, language barriers, and social norms
Support Systems	- Adequate social support and integration programs - Language instruction, skills development, employment services - Psychological help in coping with emotional challenges

Note: Table 1 illustrates the various factors that influence the readjustment experience of Uzbek returnees from South Korea to Uzbekistan (Author prepared).

Thus, Table 1 shows that the readjustment experiences of Uzbek returnees from South Korea to Uzbekistan are influenced by several factors: voluntary and forced return, reintegration difficulties, and support systems. Voluntary return involves adjustment to a changed lifestyle, cultural differences, and economic inequalities. Forced return is more challenging due to the disruption of familiar life and social networks. Difficulties in reintegration include finding suitable employment and adjusting to cultural norms. Adequate support systems, including language instruction and psychological support, are critical to successful reintegration. These factors are consistent with Kim's re-acculturation theory, which emphasizes the importance of sociocultural factors and social support in facilitating the re-acculturation process.

In fact, returnees from South Korea who voluntarily choose to return to Uzbekistan may experience a mix of emotions and challenges upon arrival. While some people feel a sense of relief and belonging when they see their families and familiar surroundings again, others have difficulty readjusting to their home country. These difficulties may be due to a variety of factors, including lifestyle changes, cultural differences, and economic disparities between South Korea and Uzbekistan. Although most of our respondents stated that they had re-adapted to Uzbekistan (5 returnees said they had readjusted), it is still important to note that many of them believe that they have not been able to re-adapt. Moreover, even those who believe they have re-adapted speak of the fact that readjustment was a long and arduous process for them. There are long debates about the culture shock that migrants experience after moving to the host country. Our findings show that culture shock and the process of re-adaptation can be equally painful and take a long time for returnees. Some of our respondents argue that they found post-migration adjustment easier compared to the positive aspects of life in Uzbekistan after their return. Although they appreciate the positive aspects of life in Uzbekistan, they also seem to miss many aspects of their previous life in South Korea. The longer they spent in the host country, the more difficult the process of readjustment seems to be. Readjustment to Uzbekistan also involved adapting to new life stages such as marriage and family responsibilities.

If you had asked me this question in the first 6 months, I would have said that I could not readjust. I had a lot of difficulties in the first year. But later you start to accept it. Sometimes people accept to stay in their home country because they have family obligations or need to get married, but in most cases, returnees had not chosen to do so because of problems with the visa or documents, because in my case I would have definitely emigrated again in the first 6 months if I had not been deported. (Bobur)

Forced returnees, on the other hand, often face greater challenges and experience a range of negative emotions due to their involuntary return. These individuals may have built a life and established social networks in South Korea, making their return to Uzbekistan particularly disruptive. The abrupt change from a potentially prosperous life in South Korea to uncertain circumstances in their home country can lead to feelings of disappointment, frustration, and even a sense of loss.

Whether the return was voluntary or forced, returned migrants may face difficulties reintegrating into the social, economic, and cultural fabric of Uzbekistan. They may have difficulty finding employment opportunities that match their skills and qualifications acquired in South Korea, leading to feelings of underutilization or dissatisfaction. In addition, the cultural adjustments required, including language barriers and social norms, can be a major challenge in re-establishing a sense of belonging and identity.

Returnees' experiences are also influenced by the level of support available to them. Adequate social support systems and integration programs offered by the government or nongovernmental organizations can play a critical role in facilitating the reintegration process. Such support may include language instruction, skills development programs, access to employment services, and psychological help in coping with the emotional challenges of return.

The experiences of migrants returning to Uzbekistan from South Korea are thus complex and multifaceted. They include a range of emotional, social, economic, and cultural factors that can significantly affect their well-being and successful reintegration. Understanding these experiences is critical for policymakers

and organizations to develop effective support mechanisms and policies that address the needs and challenges returnees face in both voluntary and forced returns.

Thus, the discussion of the experiences of returnees from South Korea in Uzbekistan can be related to Kim's re-acculturation theory, which focuses on the psychological and sociocultural processes that occur when people return to their home country after living abroad.

First, Kim's re-acculturation theory emphasizes the challenges and adjustments that returning migrants face in terms of cultural and psychological re-acculturation. The experiences described in the response, such as difficulties in reacclimating to the culture, language barriers, and lifestyle changes, are consistent with Kim's theory. Returning migrants may need to renegotiate their cultural identity, relearn social norms, and adapt to the cultural context of Uzbekistan, which can affect their overall well-being and sense of belonging. Kim's theory also highlights the concept of reintegration stress, which refers to the psychological and emotional strain that returnees experience during the re-acculturation process. The feelings of disappointment, frustration, and loss mentioned in the response can be understood within the framework of reintegration stress.

I feel like I cannot adapt to the world anymore because I emigrated three times. once to Russia and twice to South Korea, I feel like a person without a country

now. I can live anywhere but have no home anywhere... it's not easy. so, I would recommend people who want to go abroad or plan to go back to think twice about it. (Bahrom)

Returning migrants may struggle with the gap between their expectations and the reality they face upon return, which can lead to various psychological challenges. The availability and effectiveness of social support systems and integration programs mentioned in the response are consistent with Kim's notion that support from family, friends, and the community can facilitate successful re-acculturation. Furthermore, the mention of economic disparities and employment opportunities reflects the sociocultural context in which returnees navigate their reintegration process. Thus, when we link returnees' experiences to Kim's theory of re-acculturation, we can gain insight into the psychological, cultural, and sociocultural dimensions of their re-acculturation process. Understanding these factors can help in the development of support mechanisms, interventions, and policies that facilitate smoother and more successful reintegration of returnees from South Korea into Uzbekistan.

3) Return Factors

The readjustment experiences of Uzbek migrants returning to Uzbekistan from South Korea are influenced by a combination of factors, including life course differences, occupation, economic reasons, family obligations, and the concepts described in Kim's re-acculturation theory (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Return factors (Author prepared).

First, life course differences play an important role in shaping the readjustment experience. Younger return migrants find adjustment relatively easy because they have fewer family and work obligations. In contrast, older individuals may face additional challenges due to entrenched routines, family obligations, and potential generational differences. Those who have spent much of their lives in South Korea may encounter a larger cultural and social gap upon their return to Uzbekistan, requiring them to make great efforts to bridge the gap and reintegrate into the social fabric of their home country (Figure 1).

Occupation is another important factor affecting reintegration. Some returnees may have specialized skills that they acquired in South Korea, particularly in

areas such as technology or manufacturing. The compatibility of these skills with available opportunities in Uzbekistan may significantly affect their ability to reintegrate into the workforce. Mismatched skills or limited job prospects can lead to frustration, financial strain, and a sense of occupational stagnation, hindering the reintegration process. Consequently, it is often economic reasons that influence the decision to return. Returning migrants may face economic challenges both during their time in South Korea and upon their return to Uzbekistan. Economic disparities, differences in wages and job stability, and the need to find a new source of income can all impact readjustment (Figure 1). Overcoming these challenges requires access to economic support systems, entrepreneurial opportunities, and effective employment services. In addition, family

responsibilities such as caring for parents, spouses, and children or fulfilling marital obligations can also significantly impact the readjustment experience. The balancing act between family responsibilities and reintegration into a new environment can place additional pressures and demands on returning migrants.

Kim's reacculturation theory thus provides a framework for understanding the psychological and sociocultural processes involved in readjustment. It highlights the challenges associated with renegotiating cultural identities, relearning social norms, and navigating the sociocultural context of Uzbekistan. Returning migrants may experience a range of emotions, including disappointment, frustration, and loss, as they navigate the gap between their expectations and the reality they face upon return. Building social support networks, accessing cultural resources, and interventions to promote psychological well-being are important elements in enabling successful readjustment. In summary, the readjustment experience of Uzbek migrants returning to Uzbekistan from South Korea is influenced by several factors, including life course differences, occupation, economic reasons, family obligations, and the principles outlined in Kim's theory of re-acculturation. Dealing with these factors requires comprehensive support mechanisms, including job placement, vocational training programs, economic support, social support networks, and psychological interventions. In this sense, it is critical to recognize and address these factors so that we can improve the readjustment experience and promote successful integration of returning migrants.

4) Trigger of the return migration

The process of reintegrating into life in the home country, particularly for Uzbek returnees who have returned from South Korea, can be more difficult than emigrating again to the same or another country due to a variety of factors. While this analysis focuses on Uzbek returnees, similar challenges can be observed for returnees from other countries. The difficulties of reintegration can be explained by the notion of reverse culture shock and the complex interplay of personal, cultural, and contextual factors. Returnees often face unexpected challenges when reintegrating into their home country, even though they are already familiar with the culture and environment. This phenomenon can be attributed to the concept of reverse culture shock, which refers to the psychological and emotional disorientation that people experience when they return to their home culture. The expectations and assumptions they have about their home country may clash with the reality they find, leading to feelings of alienation, frustration, and a sense of being out of place.

One reason why reintegrating into the home country can be more difficult than emigrating again is the high expectations and assumptions returnees often have. They may romanticize their home country and idealize the familiar culture, language, and social dynamics. However, the reality on the ground may not match their idealized expectations, leading to feelings of disillusionment and disappointment.

In addition, reintegration can be challenging due to the changes that have occurred in the home country

during the returnee's absence. It may be that social, economic, and political changes have taken place that have altered the social landscape and created new dynamics that returnees must cope with. They may have difficulty fitting into these new dynamics and reconciling their memories of the past with current realities. Returnees may also have difficulty re-establishing social connections and support networks. Relationships with friends and family members may have changed or weakened during their absence, making it difficult to rebuild these ties. This lack of social support can increase feelings of isolation and hinder the reintegration process. When comparing the cases of returnees from other countries, one often finds similar challenges. Each country has its own cultural and contextual factors that can impact the reintegration process. For example, returnees from countries with rapid economic development may find it difficult to adapt to changes in the socioeconomic landscape of their home country, while returnees from countries with political instability may find it difficult to reintegrate into the local political environment. In summary, reintegration into the home country, such as for Uzbek returnees from South Korea, can be more difficult than re-migration to the same or another country. The concept of reverse culture shock helps explain this phenomenon by highlighting the clash between idealized expectations and the realities of the home country. The challenges of re-establishing social relationships, adapting to change, and reconciling memories of the past with the present also contribute to the difficulties faced by returnees. By understanding these dynamics, we as policymakers and aid organizations can develop targeted interventions that address the specific issues returnees face and facilitate their successful reintegration into their home country.

5. Discussion

This study addresses the challenges Uzbek returnees face in readjustment and examines the factors that influence their intention to remigrate. This study not only contributes to the existing body of knowledge but also engages in theoretical discussions to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. The study draws on several theoretical frameworks to examine the problem of Uzbek returnees' readjustment. In particular, it utilizes Kim's re-acculturation theory, which sheds light on the psychological and sociocultural processes involved in returning to one's home country after living abroad. By applying this theory, the study highlights the complexity and unique challenges Uzbek returnees face, helping to shape the analysis and interpretation of their experiences. Furthermore, the study recognizes the importance of intersectional studies in understanding the readjustment process. Recognizing that individuals' identities are shaped by multiple dimensions such as gender, age, socioeconomic status, and educational background, the study examines how these intersecting factors relate to the readjustment experiences of Uzbek returnees. This intersectional perspective increases the depth of the analysis and provides a nuanced understanding of the multiple challenges faced by different subgroups of Uzbek returnees.

In addition to theoretical discussions, the study contributes to current trends and debates in the field of

migration studies. Remigration, or the intention to return to the host country, is a complex and evolving phenomenon that has gained increasing attention in recent years. Examining the factors that influence the remigration intentions of Uzbek returnees contributes to the broader discourse on voluntary return and the factors that influence migrants' decisions to either remain in their home country or pursue further migration opportunities. This analysis provides valuable insights into ongoing debates about the sustainability of return migration programs and the factors that influence migrants' mobility aspirations. Thus, this study not only improves our understanding of the issues Uzbek returnees face in readjustment, but also engages in theoretical discussions, considers intersectional perspectives, and contributes to current trends and debates in migration research. The findings of this study have important implications for policymakers, organizations, and stakeholders seeking to support the successful reintegration of Uzbek returnees and effectively address their remigration intentions.

6. Conclusion

Thus, this study has provided important insights into the readjustment problems and remigration intentions of Uzbek returnees from South Korea. The analysis of factors influencing their readjustment experiences has revealed several important findings. First, the challenges Uzbek returnees face are multi-faceted and influenced by various factors such as cultural differences, economic disparities, language barriers, and the need to find suitable employment opportunities. These challenges affect their overall adjustment process and contribute to their intention to remigrate. In addition, this study has highlighted the importance of theoretical frameworks, particularly Kim's reacclimation theory, in understanding the psychological and sociocultural processes involved in readjustment. The application of this theoretical framework has enhanced our understanding of the experiences of Uzbek returnees and provided a valuable basis for analyzing their challenges and the interventions needed for successful reintegration. From a scholarly perspective, this study contributes to the broader field of migration studies through its intersectional approach. By recognizing the different identities and intersecting factors that shape the reintegration experience, including gender, age, socioeconomic status, and educational background, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of the challenges faced by different subgroups of Uzbek returnees. This approach enriches our understanding of the complexity of readjustment and remigration processes.

Based on the findings of this study, several suggestions can be made. First, policymakers and organizations should consider developing targeted support programs that address the specific challenges of Uzbek returnees and take into account their diverse backgrounds and circumstances. These could include language training, skills development, access to employment services, and psychological support to facilitate the reintegration process. In addition, the study highlights the need for improved policies and initiatives that promote the sustainability of remigration programs.

Understanding the factors that influence remigration intentions can help in the design and implementation of policies aimed at meeting returnees' aspirations and needs, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful reintegration. In summary, this study has shed light on the reintegration challenges and remigration intentions of Uzbek returnees from South Korea. By using theoretical frameworks, considering intersectional perspectives, and providing practical suggestions, this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on migration studies and provides valuable insights for policymakers and organizations seeking to effectively support the reintegration of Uzbek returnees.

Notes

This research project is free of conflict of interest and financial support. The study was conducted in compliance with strict ethical standards that ensure participant privacy and confidentiality. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and privacy, were strictly followed throughout the study.

Appendix

Interview questions.

1. Please tell me something about yourself and your previous experiences abroad (family, education, job, important things in your life...)

- Your family background.
- What did you study? Or a job in South Korea.
- Where have you lived or traveled to besides South Korea?
- When did you return?
- How many years have you lived in... lived?
- How and why did you make the decision to return to Uzbekistan?
- What are you doing now? How did you get to your current professional position?
- To what extent did your experience abroad help you find a job?
- What are the most important matters in your life right now? How is experience abroad impacting your life now?

2. Why did you decide to go to South Korea?

- Have you considered going to a country other than Korea?
- Did living abroad have any benefits for your country or for your family and friends?
- Who or what influenced your decision to go to South Korea?

3. How would you describe your life in South Korea?

- Specific examples of positive and negative experiences?
- Is there anything you did not expect when you arrived?
- Who has been helpful to you?

4. How did your stay plan change over time?

- What did you plan to do before you left that you would do after the planned period was over?
- How did you plan to stay during your stay?
- At the end of your stay, when you were preparing to return to Uzbekistan.
- Why and how did you decide to return to Uzbekistan?

5. What was your experience returning to Uzbekistan after your extended stay abroad?

-How did you feel when you returned to Uzbekistan? What was the emotional experience like?

-How did you experience the first month after your return?

-What was the most positive experience during the first two months after your return, and what proved to be difficult during your re-acclimation?

-Have you talked much about your experiences abroad, what was the best part of your return?

-Did you have any culture shock or different feelings before you left and after you returned home?

6. What do you think you gained or lost from your stay in South Korea?

-Are your experiences abroad valued in Uzbekistan?

-How do you think other people perceive you and think about you?

-What are important skills you gained while living in South Korea?

-Do you still have connections with friends or Koreans after you return?

-Are you satisfied with your decision to return?

7. What factors and causes influenced your plans to emigrate to South Korea again?

-Are you planning to emigrate again?

-Can you describe what was the greatest difficulty for you in readjusting?

-Would you leave Uzbekistan again if you had the opportunity to emigrate?

-How did you overcome culture shock and other difficult situations after your return/how did family factors and relatives or friends affect your adjustment process?

-Can you give any recommendations or advice to migrants who are planning to return or are facing a decision?

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